

ISSUES OF ENSURING ECONOMIC SECURITY IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article analyzes in detail the current issues of economic security in industrial enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The essence of economic security is studied from a theoretical point of view and its importance from an economic point of view is described. To implement an economic security strategy, it is necessary to develop a mechanism for its implementation.*

Keywords: *industry, industrial enterprise, economic security, indicators, external, internal, dangers, threats.*

Introduction

At the present stage of development of digital technologies, ensuring the economic security of industrial enterprises is an important task. After all, economic security serves as the basis for making decisions on socio-economic issues. Any change in the economic system is accompanied by the manifestation of various risks and threats. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” also states that in order to accelerate the development of the national economy and ensure high growth rates, it is necessary to continue the implementation of industrial policy aimed at ensuring the stability of the national economy, increasing the share of industry in the gross domestic product and an increase in industrial production by 1.4 times [1].

Therefore, one of the important tasks is to develop the leading sectors of the national economy and ensure the economic security of industrial enterprises in our country.

The problem of economic security is crucial in the context of worsening external and internal threats. Due to the fact that the level of economic security is influenced by the state of various sectors of the economy, it is necessary to identify and evaluate the development of those areas that affect the functioning of both the state and the population.

The economic security of an enterprise can be understood as the protection of its scientific, technical, technological, production and personnel potential from direct or indirect economic threats associated with the influence of the external environment, and its ability to develop flexibly.

Literature review

Issues of ensuring economic security at industrial enterprises have been studied in the works of many scientists well-known in the field of economics. An important role in the theoretical and empirical substantiation of the issues under study is played by the works of leading Western scientists, namely: T. Allison, J.K. Van Horn, H. Maule, T. Parsons, G. Tosterp and J. Schumpeter.

Issues of identifying threats to economic security are among the scientific interests of E. Oleinikov, V. Pankov, G. Pasternak, V. Ponomarev, V. Rubanov, V. Savin, V. Tambotsev, V.

Tkachenko, V. Shlemko, L. Abalkin, S. Glazyev, S. Golovnin, V. Gorodetsky, I. Lazarev, V. Medvedev, E. Oleinikov, A. Porokhovskiy, V. Senchagov and others.

A great contribution to the theoretical study of the problem of ensuring economic security was made by domestic scientists and practitioners, such as Kh. Abdulkosimov, A.E. Ishmuhammedov, D. Ortikova.

In particular, in the textbook by D. Artikova, entitled “Economic Security”[2], ideas are given about the problems of the country’s economic security, threats, its indicators, criteria and lower limit values. A special place in it is given to the influence of globalization processes on the economic security of countries, increasing the competitiveness of the economy, the place and role of regional organizations in ensuring economic security, terrorism, the secret economy, corruption and their impact on economic security.

According to economist A. Ishmukhamedov [3]: economic security is a set of internal and external conditions and factors that influence the economic system of the state and its stable development from level to level at the lowest cost, allowing maximum expression of national interests in order to fully realize potential opportunities. society, as well as the state’s ability to withstand various risks and failures.

At the same time, an analysis of publications that examine the genesis of the concept of economic security indicates both the absence of a common approach to defining this category and common views regarding the mechanisms for ensuring it. So, despite a significant number of works devoted to the analysis of the content and patterns of development of the economic security system, the conceptual apparatus of this definition requires improvement and further elaboration.

Research methodology

In the course of studying aspects of the economic security of industrial enterprises, methods such as observation, induction and deduction, time series, analysis and synthesis, monographic studies, systematic analysis, comparison and other methods were used.

Figure 1. Classification of types of economic security

Source: Systematized by author based on the study of foreign literature.

We believe that for any industrial enterprise engaged in specific economic and trade activities, the concepts of “external” and “internal” threats are purely individual. For industrial enterprises, the most significant external risks are political and economic destabilizing factors, and internal risks of economic activity associated with safety of inventory items.

Particular attention should be paid to assessments economic security of industrial enterprises, first of all, because their actively involved potential is a determining stabilizing factor in anti-crisis development, a guarantor of economic growth and maintaining the economic independence and security of the country. Problems of ensuring economic security arise for every industrial enterprise, regardless of what exactly it does, not only during periods of crisis, but also when operating in a stable economic environment, therefore, problems of economic security of industrial enterprises should be given special attention in strategic planning.

It is appropriate to consider economic security as an integral part of anti-crisis economic management. Economic crises of various types and durations are a consequence of any multi-system economy. Crises can be expressed in an increase in the gap between supply and demand, devaluation of money, an increase in the cost of living, unemployment, that is, in a deterioration in macroeconomic indicators.

Economic security has a very complex internal structure. Analysis of real processes in it, domestic and foreign experience in solving this problem allows us to highlight three of its qualitative characteristics:

1) The sustainability and stability of the national economy is the protection of all forms of property, the creation of reliable conditions and guarantees for business activity, the suppression of factors that destabilize the situation (the fight against criminal structures in the economy, the prevention of serious disruptions in the economy). distribution of income, causing social chains, etc.), presupposes;

2) The opportunity for self-development - this is especially important in the current era of harmonious development. Creating a favorable environment for investment and innovation, constant modernization of production, increasing the general professional and cultural level of workers is a necessary and mandatory condition for maintaining the stability of the national economy and its overall identity;

3) Economic independence - in the conditions of the world economy has no absolute significance. The international division of labor unites national economies. In such conditions, economic independence means that the state can control its own national resources, it is competitive in world trade, cooperation and the exchange of scientific and technological achievements, and has reached a level of production where it can participate on an equal basis. with others.

As we know, industry is a branch of production that includes the processing of raw materials, the development of subsoil, the creation of means of production and consumer goods. One of the directions of structural changes in the national economy is structural changes in the industrial complex. In order to ensure sustainable development of industrial sectors, it is represented by the introduction of new equipment and technologies into production and the processes of structural restructuring. One of the main goals of the country's structural policy is to ensure the competitiveness and economic security of industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan through structural restructuring in the industry.

Hence, it is necessary to study and analyze the structure of the industrial sector and pay special attention to the most significant and vulnerable sectors for the production of industrial products.

According to data, in January-December 2023, enterprises of the republic produced industrial products worth 655.8 trillion soums, the index of physical volume of industrial production compared to the same period in 2022 was 106.0% (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Amount of manufactured industrial products for 2023.

Source: Data from the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

An increase in industrial production means that the funds and resources of industrial enterprises have increased. A targeted and long-term sustainable development policy pursued by the state to reduce the tax burden, liberalize fiscal policy, and simplify the tax system has led to GDP growth and an increase in the share of industrial products in it.

Conclusions and recommendations

The problems associated with ensuring the economic security of industrial enterprises in our country include:

- the role and significance of the security system and economic security in economic literature is not sufficiently disclosed;
- lack of consensus among scientists in our country regarding the concept of economic security and its types;
- despite the importance of ways to ensure the economic security of industrial enterprises, the law “On Economic Security” has not yet been developed in our country;
- lack of a clear system of indicators for assessing the economic security of industrial enterprises, scientific foundations of economic security for the country, region, economic entities and each person;
- underdevelopment of the stratified system; underdevelopment of the organizational and structural system for ensuring the economic security of the enterprise.

Therefore, the project to ensure economic security industrial enterprises is a single organizational and technical complex, during the formation of which a concept for ensuring the safety of an object or a security policy is developed. It is based on a list of mandatory measures aimed at developing an action plan to protect the facility: determining the composition of the security service, its place in the organizational structure of the enterprise, its sphere of competence, rights and powers, options for action in various situations in order to avoid conflicts between departments. Their rationale usually lies precisely in the fact that many consider the requirements imposed by the security service to be unreasonably high or because the security service “sticks its

nose everywhere.” Compliance the above conditions will eliminate the possibility of such situations or resolve them quickly and painlessly.

The economic security policy determines the correct way from the organization's point of view to use communication and computing resources, rules for access to the facility, rules for handling confidential information, as well as procedures for preventing and responding to security violations.

Thus, we can note that the economic security of industrial enterprises, as a successful component of modern business, is a fairly long and continuous process, which includes not only a certain number of interrelated stages that ensure the economic security of industrial enterprises, but also a complex of intra-economic operations, which are also aimed at ensuring economic security, which in turn ensures the successful functioning of modern business.

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